

NMR advances towards structural characterization of huge protein assemblies[†]

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Abstract : A majority of cellular functions are mediated through protein-protein interaction/association. However, large assemblies of megadalton size pose a great challenge to structural investigations either by X-ray crystallography or by NMR; they may, in fact, be termed as 'black holes' so far as NMR measurement is concerned. This is due to the fact that the line widths in the NMR spectra of such huge assemblies are extremely large and often the signals are buried in the noise. In this article, we review some of the recent efforts in overcoming these problems. Firstly, there are efforts to narrow down lines by relaxation optimization, both by appropriate sample preparation and by the design of NMR pulse sequences. These direct methods aim at observing signals directly from the assemblies. Recent efforts in our laboratory have presented an alternate and indirect NMR approach, which derives its success from the NMR methods, developed for studying unfolded, partially folded and properly folded proteins with similar ease. This involves a bottom-up strategy of denaturation-dissociation followed by systematic refolding-association, wherein the observations made on the monomer carry valuable information with regard to the structural detail of the molecules in the assembly. Naturally, this approach is not limited by the size of the assembly. We have used this approach to characterize a megadalton size protein assembly, the largest ever handled by NMR till date.

Keywords : NMR, large assemblies, HNN, spin relaxation, GED.

Introduction

Protein-protein association to form large molecular species is an important step in many cellular functions^{1,2}. Examples include, ribosome, chaperone, proteasome, chromatin, multi-subunit proteins, dynamin assembly, dynein motor assembly, to name a few. The biological functions arise as a consequence of controlled and coordinated assembly formation, and thus association-dissociation processes would serve as regulatory mechanisms. There are other instances where uncontrolled associations lead to dysfunctions which turn out to be the causes of certain diseases. Recently, it has been recognized that proteins, in general, can form fibrils – which are huge self-assemblies – under certain experimental conditions^{3,4}. Large soluble oligomers are precursors to such fibrils and presumably, it is the precursors which are responsible for the disease conditions^{5,6}. Structural character-

ization of such large assemblies, which holds the clues for understanding their biological functions, has remained a difficult task. The protein data bank (PDB) which is the sole repository of structural determinations contains, as of April 2009, around 57000 entries, of which about 49000 have resulted from X-ray crystallographic investigations and the others from NMR. Classification of these on the basis of molecular masses indicates that there are very few structures of molecular mass larger than 45 kDa. The list includes both individual molecules and molecular assemblies. The largest assembly that has been characterized so far from X-ray crystallography is the 70S ribosome which has a molecular mass of 2.5 MDa^{7,8}. The largest assembly from which signals have been observed in NMR is the 900 kDa GroEL-GroES chaperone complex⁹.

From the NMR point of view the difficulty in study-

[†]In honour of Professor Jai P. Mittal.

ing large assemblies arises from the fact that the line widths are extremely large and often the signals remain buried inside the noise. This in turn arises from the fact that large molecules tumble very slowly in solution. The second problem in dealing with large molecular assemblies by NMR is the excessive crowding of peaks in the spectra. This can happen either due to (i) asymmetry of the assembly whereby different monomer units though chemically identical produce different sets of peaks, (ii) large size of the monomeric chain in homo-assemblies, or (iii) large heterogeneity in the hetero-assemblies. Fortunately, however, analysis of the genomic data seems to suggest that majority of proteins that self-assemble form symmetric structures^{10,11}. The problems associated with (ii) and (iii) can be partially overcome by selective labeling techniques which simplify the spectra. However, this will be at the cost of information in the spectra. The present review focuses on issues related to large line widths of the protein assemblies.

NMR line widths

An NMR line in a spectrum has a definite width which arises due to fluctuations in the magnetic fields at the site of the observed nucleus. These fluctuations are also responsible for the relaxation phenomena and it turns out that the lines widths are related to the transverse relaxation rates in a simple manner.

$$\Delta\nu = R_2/\pi \quad (1)$$

where, $\Delta\nu$ is the line width and R_2 is the transverse relaxation rate in Hz. Fluctuations in magnetic field arise due to molecular motions. Among the different manifestations of these motions, modulation of the dipole-dipole interaction is the dominant one and almost entirely dictates the line widths in most situations. Chemical shift anisotropy is another phenomenon which gets modulated due to motions and this also contributes to the transverse relaxation rates. The observed relaxation rate is thus intimately related to the motional characteristics of a protein molecule. The motions are characterized by various rotational correlation times and depending upon the rates of the motions, fluctuations in the fields occur at different frequencies and also with different amplitudes at each of the frequencies. This is described in terms of the spectral density function $J(\omega)$ which essentially reflects the power available at each of the frequencies. This is given by the equation¹²,

$$J(\omega) = \frac{2}{5} \left[\frac{S^2 \tau_m}{1 + \tau_m^2 \omega^2} + \frac{(1 - S^2) \tau}{1 + \tau_m^2 \omega^2} \right] \quad (2)$$

where, τ_m is the overall tumbling correlation time and τ includes the internal motions in the protein. S^2 describes the order parameter which defines the rigidity of the chain at the site of the nucleus; for ^{15}N , for example, this defines the rigidity of the N-H vector. The efficiency of relaxation of a nucleus or the relaxation rate is therefore dictated by the power available at the various frequencies as per the energy level scheme of the N-H spin system. It turns out that the ^{15}N transverse relaxation rate for an N-H vector is given by¹²,

$$\begin{aligned} R_{2\text{N}} = & \frac{1}{8} d_{\text{NH}}^2 \{4J(0) + 3J(\omega_{\text{H}} - \omega_{\text{N}}) + 3J(\omega_{\text{N}}) \\ & + 6J(\omega_{\text{H}}) + J(\omega_{\text{H}} + \omega_{\text{N}})\} + \left\{ \frac{\gamma_{\text{N}}}{6} \{4J(0) + 3J(\omega_{\text{N}})\} \right. \\ & + \frac{c_{\text{H}}^2}{6} J(\omega_{\text{H}}) + \frac{1}{8} \sum_{\text{HH}} d_{\text{HH}}^2 \{J(0) \\ & \left. + 3J(\omega_{\text{H}}) + 6J(2\omega_{\text{H}})\} \right\} \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

where; $d_{\text{NH}} = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \gamma_{\text{H}} \gamma_{\text{N}} \frac{\hbar}{2\pi} (r_{\text{NH}}^{-3})$;

$$c_{\text{N}} = \frac{\omega_{\text{N}}(\sigma_{\parallel} - \sigma_{\perp})}{\sqrt{3}} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_{\parallel} - \sigma_{\perp} = -160 \text{ ppm}, \quad r_{\text{NH}} =$$

1.02 Å; ω_{N} and ω_{H} are the nitrogen and proton Larmor frequencies, respectively, $\sigma_{\parallel} - \sigma_{\perp} = -160$ ppm represents the chemical shift anisotropy. The first term in eq. (3) gives the contribution of the N-H dipolar relaxation, the second term yields the contribution of chemical shift anisotropy relaxation of nitrogen, the third term is due to chemical shift anisotropy of protons and the last term is due to proton-proton dipolar contribution. It is clear from eqs. (2) and (3) together that slow motions represented by $J(0)$ make a major contribution to the transverse relaxation rates and thus to the line widths. Straight forward calculations from the above equations reveal that the line widths of protein signals (^{15}N and ^1H) can vary from few Hz in small proteins to several hundreds of Hz in large (megadalton size) protein assemblies. We hasten to add that slow conformational exchanges cause further complications by their line broadening effects depending on

the rates of conformational exchanges. This, however, has to be ascertained separately in each case by artificially altering the exchange rates by changing temperatures or other solution conditions.

Line narrowing by deuteration

It is evident from the above discussion that dipole-dipole interaction between remote ^1H spins in a protein molecule is an important contributor to relaxation and thus to line widths in the NMR spectra of proteins. The magnitude of this interaction depends on the magnetic moments of the protons and thus it would seem that replacing some protons by deuterons which have 1/6th the magnetic moment of the former, would reduce the interaction and hence the efficiency of the dipole-dipole relaxation. Consequently, this is expected to sharpen the lines in the spectrum. Indeed perdeuteration of a protein molecule and observing NMR signal in H_2O solutions, where the amides will have protons and the rest of the protons will be replaced by deuterons, does produce very sharp signals for the amide protons. However, complete replacement of all the protons by deuterons also leads to loss of information. This hampers structural determination by the ^1H - ^1H NOE based methods. Therefore, often a compromised solution is derived by partial deuteration of the protein molecule (to say $\sim 70\%$) whereby fair amount of line narrowing is achieved and at the same time there are enough protons to provide inter-proton distance information as structural inputs. Selective deuteration¹³ wherein only some protons in each amino acid residue are replaced by deuterons is another strategy to sharpen the lines and also gain resolution enhancement by reducing the crowding of peaks in the NMR spectra. However, this is an expensive and laborious proposition for routine exploitation. For certain applications, the entire protein except the methyl groups are deuterated and signals are observed exclusively from the methyl groups (see below).

The TROSY experiment

Kurt Wuthrich and coworkers designed a novel strategy based on the fact that the components of a multiplet in an NMR spectrum can differ in their line widths and this arises due to the so-called cross-correlation effect. Different transverse relaxation mechanisms, especially, dipole-dipole relaxation and chemical shift anisotropy relaxation can interfere destructively in some components

and constructively in some others resulting in differential line broadening effects in different components of a multiplet. Experimental strategies based on this constitute the so-called Transverse Relaxation Optimized Spectroscopy (TROSY)¹⁴.

In proteins, the amide signals are doublets in the NMR spectrum and the two lines have intrinsically different line widths because of the TROSY effect. The upfield component is narrower compared to the downfield component because of the destructive interference of the two relaxation mechanisms mentioned above. Similarly, in the ^{15}N doublet, the downfield component is sharper than the upfield component. This effect is also dependent on the molecular mass, being more prominent for large molecular masses. This is why the strategy holds promise for investigating large molecular assemblies. However, the TROSY effect is also dependent on the magnetic field, since chemical shift anisotropy is directly dependent on the strength of the magnetic field, while dipole-dipole relaxation is solely dependent on the tumbling correlation times. Chemical shift anisotropy increases with field and thus there is an optimum where the TROSY effects can be maximally and beneficially seen. Fig. 1 shows the dependence of the computed line widths on the field strengths for different correlation times of the tumbling molecules in solution (reproduced with permission¹⁵). It

Fig. 1. Calculated ^1H (left) and ^{15}N (right) line widths as a function of spectrometer frequencies for a chosen set correlation times of 20, 60, 320 ns. These represent the wide range of molecular masses (reproduced with permission¹⁵).

is evident that maximal benefits are seen for field strengths of around 1 GHz and for molecules tumbling very slowly with correlation times larger than 100 ns. Under normal

solution conditions of NMR experiments on proteins (pH 5–7, temperature 25–40, 100–200 mM salt, 0.5–1.5 mM protein concentration) a protein of molecular mass of 10 kD (~90 amino acids) would have a correlation time of ~4–5 ns and assuming that the correlation time increases roughly linearly with molecular weight, a correlation time of 100 ns would correspond to a molecular mass of 200–250 kD. TROSY and a few improvements thereof, namely, CRINEPT and CRIPT¹⁶ were used to observe signals from a 900 kD GroES-GroEL complex protein assembly⁹.

Kay and coworkers extended the TROSY idea to observe methyl signals^{17–20} in uniformly deuterated proteins except at the methyl groups. Here the destructive interference occurs between ^1H - ^1H and ^1H - ^{13}C dipolar relaxation mechanisms. This is independent of the magnetic field and thus the so-called methyl-TROSY offers benefits at all magnetic fields; this is in contrast to the ^1H - ^{15}N TROSY discussed above. Of course in such an experiment one gets signals only from the methyl groups. Even so this is of great importance in large molecular systems wherein the methyl groups contribute significantly to the hydrophobic core of the protein system. Kay and coworkers used this strategy to study protein dynamics in the 20S proteasome assembly (Mr ~ 670 kD)^{18,20}. Recently, Amero *et al.*²¹ combined the methyl-TROSY with the rapid acquisition method, SOFAST-HMQC²² to observe signals rapidly (3 seconds) in a 468 kD protein assembly (TET2 homo-dodecamer).

Denaturation-dissociation and stepwise renaturation-association strategy

In the above described NMR studies on large protein assemblies, a bottom-up strategy was used wherein the monomers were first investigated in detail and then it was observed that when the assembly was reconstituted the NMR signals as observed from the new methods preserved their positions as in the monomers indicating that the monomers preserved their conformations even on assembly formation. This is a fortuitous situation. More often than not, it would happen that the monomers are difficult to obtain in solution, or when obtained they are not stable or have different conformations. Moreover, the information derived will be limited to the small set of signals observed from the assemblies.

In situations where the monomers have a very high tendency to self-assemble, thereby becoming not easily

accessible in the folded form, a strategy – which relies on first dissociating the assembly into the smaller monomers by use of external agents, and then reassembling them in a controlled manner by removal of the external agent, and simultaneously monitoring the association process systematically – can be conceived. The ensuing transient association involving different segments of the protein leads to exchange processes which in turn lead to differential line broadening along the polypeptide chain, and structural characterization of the intermediate species provides insights into the structure of the assembly. The advantage here would be that while monitoring the signals of the monomer, we would be deriving information on the multimeric species. This strategy is schematically shown in Fig. 2. Clearly, such a strategy would not depend on the size of the assembly, and moreover, would provide high resolution detail into the structures of the molecules in the assembly. This approach requires that

Fig. 2. Schematic bottom-up strategy proposed by us for studying large protein self-assemblies: The assembly is dissociated by using external agents and as the assembly is systematically reconstituted by slow removal of the external agent, the changes in the NMR signals coming from the monomers are monitored.

the dissociation process by the external agent be reversible. However, some times a complication could arise in that the dissociation may lead to denaturation or unfolding of the protein. In those cases, the denaturation process should also be reversible. If this is ensured, a bonus from this would be that one could follow the systematic folding of the protein as well, as the denaturant is slowly removed. This has its own value in the context of 'protein-folding problem'.

However, if the protein gets unfolded in the process

of dissociation of the assembly, NMR analysis is largely hampered. This is because of the fact that loss of spectral resolution and dispersion renders the assignment of resonances a formidable task. This is illustrated in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Dissociation of the assembly can lead to unfolding of the protein molecule. The HSQC spectrum of the assembly (A) shows very few peaks, which originate from the flexible regions of the assembly. The right panel (B) shows the HSQC spectrum of the dissociated monomer. This shows the expected number of peaks for the monomer, but the narrow chemical shift dispersion along the proton axis is indicative of unfolding of the protein.

Therefore one is confronted with another problem, namely, improving resolution in the spectra to be able to investigate unfolded and partially folded proteins. Such problems are encountered in characterizing ‘intrinsically unfolded proteins (IUP)²³ and in protein folding studies as well, where one has to deal with a variety of intermediates along the folding pathway of a given protein; the intermediates are by and large partially folded species containing several regions of highly flexible chains. In this context, methodologies which exploit the relatively better ^{15}N and ^{13}C chemical shift dispersions in both folded and unfolded proteins would be extremely helpful. This issue has been addressed by several groups in the past^{24–38}. Among these, the HNN and HN(C)N suite of experiments, developed in our laboratory^{24–28} have proved extremely successful in dealing with unfolded and partially folded proteins^{39–68}. These spread the peaks in the 3D spectra using two ^{15}N axes and generate correlations between three consecutive residues along the polypeptide chain. Another important feature of these experiments is that they generate patterns consisting of positive and negative peaks and these are sensitive to the nature of amino

acid residues in triplets of consecutive residues. Glycines, alanines, serines, threonines and prolines have special roles to play in this context^{26–28}. They generate series of start points for the sequential assignment process, and also serve as check points resulting in unambiguous assignments. The robustness of these experiments is such that even when one observes only a subset of the expected peaks in the HSQC spectra, they can be sequentially connected without ambiguity. This way we were able to characterize the flexible portion of a 160 kD aggregate formed by barstar under acidic pH conditions⁶⁹. Thus the HNN and HN(C)N suite of experiments provide a convenient tool for step-wise investigation of the assembly process as described in the previous paragraphs.

Structural insights into the megadalton size GED self assembly

GTPase Effector Domain (GED), is a crucial domain of dynamin responsible for its self-assembly. This assembly is a prerequisite for clathrin-mediated endocytosis by the dynamin protein¹. We observed that isolated GED forms a huge assembly of ~ 5 MDa in aqueous solutions⁴⁶. To our knowledge, no structural information is available on this assembly from any of the techniques to date. None of the previously described approaches, namely, deuteration, or ^1H - ^{15}N TROSY or combinations thereof, proved successful in producing NMR signals belonging to the core of the assembly. Fortunately, however, the assembly could be reversibly dissociated into monomers by the use of denaturing agents such as Gdn-HCl. This meant that the strategy described in the previous section could be applied to follow the assembly process. Indeed, as we describe below in some detail extremely valuable insights could be derived for the structure of the molecules in the assembly at residue level detail.

Fig. 4 shows the complete assignments in the ^1H - ^{15}N HSQC spectrum obtained by analyzing the HNN spectrum of GED denatured by 6 M Gdn-HCl⁴⁴. This provides the starting point for following the assembly process of the protein as the denaturant concentration is progressively reduced. Figs. 5 and 6 show the results of such a titration⁴⁶. The protein progressively folds to form helices in different segments and this is followed by circular dichroism and secondary chemical shifts. While the former indicates overall helix formation, the latter pro-

vides residue level progression of the helical propensities (Fig. 6, unpublished results). It is evident that when Gdn concentration is reduced from 6 M to 4 M a dramatic shift in the structural propensity occurs; H^α secondary shifts change from positive (indicative of β -propensity) to negative (indicative of α -helical propensity) values almost entirely along the sequence. These grow further as the Gdn concentration is further reduced. Besides, the progressive line broadening and disappearance of peaks in the HSQC spectra (Fig. 5A) and changes in ^{15}N transverse relaxation rates (Fig. 5B) display progressive changes in the motional characteristics (ms- μ s time scale) which iden-

Fig. 6. Plots of H^α sequence corrected secondary chemical shifts for GED in 6 M, 4 M and 2 M Gdn-HCl. Calculation is performed using random coil values by Schwarzingger *et al.*⁷⁰.

tify regions engaged in transient structure formation and concomitant self-association. In other words, at the intermediate steps there is equilibrium between partially folded monomers and associated multimers, with the association involving different folded segments of the polypeptide chain. Figs. 5C and 5D indicate that the peaks which disappear belong to the helical segments of the polypeptide chain and these have acquired helical propensities prior to the stage of complete vanishing. Thus it follows that the polypeptide chain progressively folds into helices and these then form the interior core of the assembly. Fig. 7 displays a model of self-association so derived from the NMR data. The intra-molecular folding of the chain is based on complementarities of electrostatic potential surfaces of two neighboring helices, flexibility of the intervening loop as observed by the NMR data, and likely packing of hydrophobic surfaces of the helices formed. Although the mode of intermolecular association needs better substantiation, that the monomers fold into helices and these constitute the core of the assembly stands beyond question.

Concluding remarks and future prospects

Large protein assemblies (homo- and hetero-assemblies) are a common occurrence in cell biology. While in some these are functional requirements, they are a source of diseases in some others. Structural characterization of such large molecular assemblies poses great challenges. From the NMR point of view, this warrants innovative strategies and development of NMR methods to overcome problems of large line widths. Naturally, this has attracted substantial attention world wide and different kinds of approaches are used. While 'direct methods' trying to observe signals from the assemblies directly have shown great promise, they would still reach limiting situations. On the other hand, the 'indirect methods' based on observing the monomers as the association progresses do not have such limits. The NMR lines in the monomers would be sharp and are thus amenable to many pulse sequence manipulations. The GED assembly reviewed here is the largest self-assembly (~ 5 MDa) characterized by NMR so far. This is particularly important considering that no prior information was available on this system from any other methods; in all previous cases where direct methods were used to observe signals and derive

Fig. 7. Schematic showing the step-wise helix formation, folding and self-association in the Gdn-HCl titration : A model for the assembly is derived. Box on the left side indicates that ~ 350 molecules are required for the formation of ~ 5 MDa size protein assemblies. The size of the box is a rough estimate of what can be enclosed inside a sphere of radius 22.4 nm (the hydrodynamic radius of the assembly derived from dynamic light scattering experiments⁴⁰).

some solution structural information the crystal structures were already known. However, a shortcoming of the indirect approach is that it cannot provide details of the organization inside the assembly – is there any symmetry in the association, what are the inter-monomer interactions?, etc. Thus, a combination of the two approaches would help throw light on the organization of the molecules in the assemblies. Fortunately, however, analysis of the genomic data seems to suggest that most proteins tend to assemble into symmetric forms^{10,11}. All these would have great implications for understanding biological functions where protein-protein associations play crucial roles.

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